

Impact of Social Media Usage on Emotional Maturity Among College Students

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Abstract

As the influence of social media continues to grow, it becomes increasingly important to gain a deeper understanding of how it affects the emotional and spiritual well-being of individuals, particularly at the critical stage of graduation. The current study was carried out to find the difference in emotional maturity between the social media users and non-social media users. The study included the 600 graduate students of the Sri Ganganagar district, and it involved the survey method to measure the emotional maturity scale through a standard questionnaire. The study inferred that social media use negatively affects the emotional maturity of the graduate students of the study area, there is significant difference in emotional maturity among urban, rural, boy, and girl social media users of Sri Ganganagar district, Rajasthan.

Keywords Social Media Usage, Emotional Maturity, College Students.

Introduction

Social media has undoubtedly transformed the way we connect, communicate, and engage with each other. Over the past two decades, it has grown into a global phenomenon, profoundly impacting human populations across the world (Qualman, 2012). The connection between social media and the human population is extensively explored, highlighting its profound impact on society, culture, and individual life (Baym, 2015).

On the other side, the impact of social media on mental health is a topic of growing concern. The constant exposure of social media can contribute to feelings of inadequacy, anxiety, and depression. The human population, especially the younger generation, is grappling with the pressure to present a perfect online persona, leading to concerns about self-esteem and body image issues (Cain, 2018; Freitas *et al*, 2017).

Objective of study

As the influence of social media continues to grow, it becomes increasingly important to gain a deeper understanding of how it affects the emotional and spiritual well-being of individuals, particularly at the critical stage of graduation. Exploring the intricacies of emotional maturity in the context of social media usage can provide valuable insights into the potential implications for this demographic. Therefore, the current study was carried out to find the difference in emotional maturity between the social media users and non-social media users.

Review of Literature

In concern to youth, the increased usage of social media is capable to alter the emotional maturity. It can influence their emotional development in both positive and negative way (Buckingham, 2007). In positive impacts youth may become self-expressive, more open-minded, emotionally mature as they engage with people from various backgrounds, can build an own support network. In negative impacts, it can cause the feelings of inadequacy and envy, become a victim of isolation, online harassment, and bullying. Unquestionably, the emotional maturity is a determinant for the social evolution and civilisation (Amram, 2009; Buckingham, 2007; Zohar, 2012).

Methodology

The current research work has descriptive research design since it aimed to describe the emotional maturity of a population. It involved the survey method through a standard

questionnaire to know the level of emotional maturity of the graduate students of Sri Ganganagar district, Rajasthan. The current research work is based on the population variable such as social media users and non-user of social media users. Thus, the research used the stratified sampling method. Accordingly, the samples were taken to know the emotional maturity from following eight different population groups.

1. **UB-SMU**: Urban Boy Social Media User Graduate Students
2. **RB-SMU**: Rural Boy Social Media User Graduate Students
3. **UG-SMU**: Urban Girl Social Media User Graduate Students
4. **RG-SMU**: Rural Girl Social Media User Graduate Students
5. **UB-NSMU**: Urban Boy Non-Social Media User Graduate Students
6. **RB-NSMU**: Rural Boy Non-Social Media User Graduate Students
7. **UG-NSMU**: Urban Girl Non-Social Media User Graduate Students
8. **RG-NSMU**: Rural Girl Non-Social Media User Graduate Students

In the current research, the 600 graduate student samples were taken from the six selected colleges of study area. The students were asked to fill the standard questionnaires for the measurement of emotional maturity. Among the 600 graduate students, the 300 students were taken as social media users and 300 students as non-social media users. Further, from each set of 300 graduate students, the 150 were taken as boys and 150 as girls graduate students. From each set of 150 boy and 150 girl students were divided into urban and rural groups. The full composition of the samples is shown in the figure (Figure-1).

Figure 1: Structure of the sample on the scale of three variables (Social media usages, Gender, and locality)

To assess and quantify emotional maturity levels among the graduate student, a standardized psychological assessment measure was employed. The study used a customised Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS) adopted from Singh and Bhargava (1988). The adopted Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS) contained 40 questions and scored on the 5-point Likert scale with 200 absolute score. For the suitability and to make the emotional maturity and spiritual intelligence on a single scale, the study implemented the reverse scoring system that suggests linkage of higher score with greater emotional maturity and lower score with poorer emotional.

After collection of the primary data, the descriptive statistics were used to summarize the survey responses, providing an overview of the participants' characteristics and self-reported levels of emotional maturity and spiritual intelligence. Subsequently, inferential statistical methods, such as t-tests were employed to compare the mean scores (hypothesis testing) of emotional maturity and spiritual intelligence between the social media users and non-users.

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical guidelines to ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to the commencement of the study.

Result and Discussion

The study found that the average value of the emotional maturity scale (EMS) for the social media users as 117.61 and value of the emotional maturity scale (EMS) for the non-social media users as 135.88 (Figure-2). It reveals that the value of emotional maturity scale (EMS) is found to be less in the social media users. It provides a confirmation that the use of social media among graduate students is responsible for the decline in the emotional maturity. Few studies have also endorsed the similar results and provided the justification for declined emotional maturity due to decreased empathy. As social media allows for virtual connections, it creates a sense of detachment from real-world social cues and face-to-face interactions. This lack of in-person engagement may impede the development of empathy and the ability to recognise and respond to the emotional states of others or emotional immaturity (McKenna and Bargh, 1999; Slater, 2002).

Other studies claim for the decline in emotional maturity due to fear of missing out (FOMO) on social experiences or events portrayed on social media. It can create anxiety, stress, and a preoccupation with constantly checking and updating one's online presence. This can distract from developing emotional resilience and the ability to be present in the moment (Hetz et al, 2015; Milyavskaya et al, 2018).

It was observed that the instant gratification mindset also contributing to decline in emotional maturity through social media usages. As social media emphasis on immediate feedback and constant stimulation that can foster an instant gratification mindset. It may hinder the development of patience, delayed gratification, and emotional resilience and leads to emotional immaturity (Chandak, 2022; Hill et al, 2024).

Additionally, the study analysed the emotional maturity among different categories of graduate students based on gender and locality. The study found that RG-NSMU (Rural Girl-Non-Social Media User Graduate Students) and RB-NSMU (Rural Boy Non-Social Media User Graduate Students) exhibited the highest values of the emotional maturity (142.44 and 142.20). Correspondingly, UG-SMU (Urban Girl Social Media User Graduate Students) and UB-SMU (Urban Boy Social Media User Graduate Students) exhibited the lowest values of the emotional maturity (111.45 and 115.32) (Figure-3 and Figure-4).

The in-depth investigation reveals that students with rural locality exhibited the higher values of the emotional maturity (142.44, 142.20, 124.52, and 119.13) rather than the students with urban locality (130.88, 128.01, 115.32, and 111.45) in both social media users and non-social media users' categories. The possible reason can be presumed that the rural-social ambience like to favour in development of the emotional maturity in youths. The social environment and cultural context in which an individual grows up can significantly influence their emotional development and maturity (Kent, 2006; Scott et al, 2018). In the case of students from rural areas, the prevailing rural social ambience may have negative effects on their emotional maturity. Further, this inference can also be supported by the concept of close-knit communities. As, rural areas often foster close-knit communities with strong social ties and support networks. This sense of belonging and community support can contribute to emotional stability, resilience, and the development of empathy and interpersonal skills, which are essential components of emotional maturity (Bridge, 2002; Tuitjer and Küpper, 2020).

Likewise, the students (boy) exhibited the higher values of the emotional maturity (142.20, 130.88, 124.52 and 115.32) rather than the students (girl) (142.44, 128.01, 119.13, and 111.45) in both social media users and non-social media users' categories. The possible reason can be presumed that the male is generally more emotionally stable than the female (Bianchin and Angrilli, 2012; Brebner, 2003). But the gender differences in emotional maturity may be influenced by socialization processes, cultural expectations, and gender roles (Brody, 2000; Brody, 2008).

Figure 2: Distribution of Emotional Maturity in the sampled students

Figure 3: Average value of Emotional Maturity in different categories of graduate students.

Figure 4: Status of the Emotional Maturity in SMU and NSMU graduate students

Conclusion

The present research work carried out to know the impact of social media usage on emotional maturity in graduate students. The study found the following conclusions:

1. The social media use negatively affect the emotional maturity of the graduate students of the study area.
2. There is significant difference in emotional maturity of urban and rural social media users.
3. There is significant difference in emotional maturity of Boys and Girls social media users.

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